

THE PROCESS OF INCLUSION OF NEOLOGISMS INTO UZBEK LANGUAGE AND ITS ROLE IN THE LIFE OF SOCIETY

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***Annotation:** The article provides brief information about the methods and history of the Uzbek language's development. The role of neologisms in the enrichment of our language and the processes of their introduction into our language are discussed. With the help of the analysis of examples, aspects of relationship of neologisms with social life are considered.*

***Keywords:** Neologisms, lexeme, vocabulary, dictionary, globalization, science, assimilation words.*

Each language reflects the whole being of the nation. As our wise people say "Language is the mirror of the nation". Language embodies history and traditions of the entire nation. It is important for the new generation to preserve their mother tongue, enrich it, and increase its prestige. In this way, the issues of developing alternative options for the use of necessary terms, phrases and concepts in the fields of information communication technologies, science and technology are becoming a topical theme for the current era.

In today's globalization process, every field is continuously developing and progressing. The development of diplomatic relations, the technological development of social life, and rapid growth of scientific fields are causing transition of words from one language to another. Uzbek language was not excluded from this process. The lexicon of Uzbek language is getting richer due to borrowed words - neologisms. The lexicon is a language that is closely related to the society and reflects any innovations and changes in it in other spheres. Most of the neologisms that serve to enrich the lexicon of the Uzbek language are words and phrases that came from English language. One of the main reasons for this is the international recognition of English language and the fact that the world's leading companies and organizations work in this language.

In Greek, neos is "new", logos is composed of "word" units, and the concept of neologism is a word that expresses new things and concepts that have appeared due to the development of society and vital needs¹. At first, the words that seem like an

¹ National encyclopedia of Uzbekistan. - Volume 12. 2000-2006.103p

unusual part of the language, after a while, become completely embedded in the language and lose their novelty properties.

We know that language is enriched mainly through two main sources. These are internal and external sources. The changes in social life during the occupation of the former Soviet Union caused the old words to fall out of use and the new words to decline. During this period, not only Russian, but also Chinese, English, French and Spanish words entered our language on the basis of Russian¹.

If we take into account that the English language has a special place in every sphere of society's life in the current rapidly developing period, we can see that our language has already acquired a large fund through English neologisms. English is a language belonging to the Indo-European language family. Nowadays, many neologisms have entered our language from English and the ways of their reduction are also different. That is, if the exact name of new word in Uzbek does not exist or if it is considered necessary for our language, it is accepted. For example, words and sentences representing new concepts such as telephone (telephone), computer (computer), telefax (telefax) can be found a lot in works of art, radio broadcasts, information technologies, media and social media.

In addition, we can cite many examples of various neologisms that have become an integral part of our daily life but are not included to "Explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language"². For example, hamburger, flash, smartphone, notebook, coca cola, etc., as long as these words are entering the Uzbek language as the language and time develop³.

The introduction of such new concepts into the language and their place is helping to strengthen the concreteness and expressive potential of the speaker's speech. Politicians and speakers use many neologisms related to their fields in expressing their speeches. Including words such as airfield, briefing, contract, essay, correspondence have a limited scope of use.

Dictionaries play a key role in correcting the neologisms that have reached our language. Currently, more than 500 English diminutive words are explained in the new edition of the "Explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language". In addition, there are more than 350 words in the "Explanatory dictionary of English words reduced to Uzbek"⁴. Examples are as following:

Reportage (eng- deliver, report) is an information genre of journalism.

¹ Analysis of several neologisms that entered the Uzbek language from English. M. Yolchiyeva.440 p.

²An explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language. 5 volumes

³ National encyclopedia of Uzbekistan. - Volume 12. 2000-2006

⁵ Hamrayeva Y.Principles of creating an educational ideographic dictionary of the Uzbek language : Candidate of Philological Sciences ...dissertation.autoreferat. - T.

A blog (eng, web log, web journal) is a form of a website in which articles are written chronologically.

A blogger is a creator of a website or page.

Interview (eng, interview, meeting) genre of journalism. Interview of a journalist with one or more persons on current issues.

Pamphlet (eng, pamphlet - a piece of paper) is a journalistic work that exposes a political system, social reality, activities of one or another group and group.

Show (eng, show, show) is a luxurious public spectacle

A manager is a person who is not the owner of a company or enterprise, but has a deep knowledge of the laws and regulations of management.

Broker (eng, broker) is a broker - certain individuals who mediate in the conclusion of sales transactions on stock, commodity, and currency exchanges.

Businessman (eng, businessman) is a person engaged in business.

Selfie (eng, selfie) is a small photo of a person taken with a small hand or a selfie stick.

Camping- (eng, camping) a summer camp with tented or light-built houses and parking for cars.

Cottage (eng. cottage, country house, peasant house) house

Language is a reflection of national spirituality, education and culture. In many hadiths, it is not for nothing that it is said that the beauty of a person is in his language. As a result of the prosperity of the language, the literacy and scientific potential of the people also increases. In short, neologisms are freely used in every aspect of life today. The free use of borrowed words in our language helps to refine the manner of expression, to clearly express the speaker's thoughts and to increase the attractiveness of the speech. In addition, it helps the listener to focus on the specific and meaningful meaning presented in the context.

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